

Research

Organic Geochemical Evaluation of the Lower Cretaceous Sembar Formation to Identify Shale-Gas Potential from the Southern Indus Basin Pakistan

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Abstract: In this research, we evaluated the shale gas potential of Sembar Formation (Lower Cretaceous) from four different wells, i.e., Well TE-1, Well TE-2, Well TE-3, and Well TE-4 of the Southern Indus Basin, Pakistan. Seventy-eight samples have been analyzed for this study by means of Total Organic Carbon (TOC), Rock-Eval analysis, Vitrinite Reflectance (R_o), and Geochemical logs. The Lower Cretaceous Sembar Formation in the study area is mainly composed of shales and minor traces of siltstone and sandstone. Sembar Formation in the Southern Indus Basin is organically rich with an average TOC of (2.05 wt. %). The shales of Sembar Formation has adequate potential to generate hydrocarbons. The mean genetic potential is 4.69 mg HC/g rock. The HI values range from 5.96-505 mg HC/g TOC with an average value of 144.45 mg HC/g TOC. Whereas, the OI values range from 3.90-306.66 mg CO₂/g TOC with an average value of 45.43 mg CO₂/g TOC. The Hydrogen Index data, HI vs T_{max} cross plot, and Van krevelen Diagram (HI vs OI) show the Sembar Formation has type II & type III kerogen, which are mainly oil and gas prone. Organic-rich shales of the Lower Cretaceous Sembar Formation in the Southern Indus Basin are thermally mature. The average T_{max} values are (450 °C), the mean Production Index is 0.38, whereas the calculated Vitrinite Reflectance based on burial history is 1.5 (%). On the basis of current investigations, it is concluded that sufficient vertical thickness of organic-rich facies, their lateral continuity, High TOC content, appropriate Kerogen type, thermal maturity reflecting oil– gas generation zone, an indigenous hydrocarbon exists within the Formation. Thus the Sembar Formation has the potential to produce unconventional hydrocarbons in the Southern Indus Basin.

Keywords: *Shale gas, Total organic carbon, Kerogen, Thermal maturity, Genetic potential*

Introduction

In 1821 in the eastern part of the United States in the Appalachian Basin, shale gas was first discovered (Curtis, 2002), however till 1976. The shale gas remained individually producing within the Devonian & Mississippian of the Appalachian Basin in the USA (Selley, 2012). In the previous decades, regarding the development and extensive-ranging development of hydraulic fracturing and horizontal good drilling tools and so forth, in North America, a "revolution of shale gas" has been hurled, which has extended globally. China contributed to the "revolution" as well. The Indus Basin, comprised of sediments of Precambrian-recent, is one of the major sedimentary basins of Pakistan. In the Sulaiman-Kirthar fold belt of Indus Basin, prospective hydrocarbon source rocks occurred in the Middle Jurassic Chiltan formation and Lower Cretaceous Sembar Formation. In this region, hydrocarbons exploration faces lots of challenges due to the complex geology of the area. The research zone is under exploration & the encroachment of petroleum exploration & production tools offers optimism for the worthwhile hydrocarbon resources discovery. At outcrop and subsurface level, a detailed geological investigation is required due to the preservation potential, migration, and petroleum generation of the layers visible within the research region. Sembar Formation indicates vertical variation in the litho-facies accumulation & very dense organic-rich clays has been encountered in some portions of the basin. Above 827,365 km² area has been occupied by the sedimentary basin in Pakistan (Onshore is almost 611,307 km² and Offshore is about 216,058 km²) in contrast to the whole region of 796,095 km². This sedimentary basin is deepened with a concentrated sequence of shale rocks act as a source & has had a proven petroleum system. Besides oil & gas reserves within the conventional reservoirs, a major amount of gas has been confined in the unconventional reservoirs containing coal-bed methane, shale gas & tight gas. In recent estimations, it seems that Pakistan is granted about 200 Tcf of unconventional gas reserves in the shale rocks as well as proven conventional gas reserves (Pacwest consulting partners, 2011). Shale gas has covered up 70% space of Pakistan (Kuuskraa et al., 2013), which has been identified by PacWest consulting partners (2011).

Our research, tries to explore the source rock perspective of the Lower Cretaceous Sembar Formation in Well TE-1, Well TE-2, Well TE-3, and Well TE-4 in the Southern Indus Basin employing geochemical analysis, geochemical logs, Rock-Eval Pyrolysis, and burial records. For the primary estimations of shale gas reservoirs, in-place reserves along vigorous association to the

researches related to geology are vastly taken into consideration an excellent tool. The methodology of the use of outcrop primarily based geological research, volumetric & gas content is employed by the British Geological Survey (BGS) to have a look at the Carboniferous Bowland shale gas geology & reserve estimate. Correspondingly shale gas success has significantly prejudiced by thorough geological research & exploitation of successive geo-modeling of the Michigan, Antrim shale of Devonian age, Caney Shale, Barnett Shale, Antrim Shale, Devonian Shale, Floyd Shale, Alabama, Oklahoma Conasauga Shale, Pearsall shale, Haynesville shale, Albany shale, Alabama Fayetteville shale, Marcellus Shale, Arkansas, Louisiana, Gothic shale, Illinois Basin; Texas, Devonian shales, Utica shale, Appalachian Basin; Chattanooga & Ohio shales, New York & Ohio, Woodford shale, Oklahoma Colorado; Collingwood Utica Shale. This research is very important for a better understanding of the type of kerogen, maturity, source rock quality, indigenous and non-indigenous hydrocarbon character, and the expulsive & non-expulsive history of the source rock of Sembar Formation, which impedes comprehensive analysis of the petroleum system.

The biggest petroleum-producing area in Pakistan is the Southern Indus Basin. Natural gas, oil, and coal have founded in this region. This region has the 9th biggest assets of the world shale oil, which has been reported by the latest (Kuuskraa et al., 2013) assessments. This area has 9.1 billion barrels of shale oil, which is sufficient for almost 20 years of the country's needs. If we talk about the gas reserves in the country, which is according to the calculations, are 105 Ctf (cubic trillion feet). The key foundation of these hydrocarbon reserves is restricted predominantly to Sembar & Ranikot formations in the Southern Indus Basin. According to (Ahmad et al., 2013), the detailed investigation of the area has not yet been commenced, i.e., geochemical analysis, except a few related to the Cretaceous sequence. The goal of this research is to investigate the potential reservoir and source rocks of Sembar Formation and other sources of oil in the zone through different geochemical approaches. This research is primarily based on TOC, Rock-Eval Pyrolysis, Geochemical logs, and Vitrinite Reflectance. This study is aimed to extend the exploration activities in the area by means of focusing on the prospective reservoir and source rocks as well as the petroleum system of the area. Hopefully, this research will develop novel perspectives of hydrocarbon richness and support in spreading the resources which are challenging to trace and produce. Finally, this research will help geoscientists working in the area and for the economic evaluation of the basin.

Geology and Tectonics

The biggest onshore basin in Pakistan is the sedimentary Indus Basin, incorporating approximately 138,000 square km's of an area. The area of study in this research is the Southern Indus Basin (Figure 1). The geology of the target area is very complex, comprising Sindh Monocline, Kirthar fold-belt, Thar platform, and Karachi Trough. Towards the west, the Southern Indus Basin is confined by Axial Belt, towards north by Sukker Rift, which is made up of two Highs called Mari Kandhkot & Jacobabad High. The Central Indus Basin is detached from Southern Indus Basin due to Sukker Rift. Towards east by Indian Shield and the south by the Arabian Sea. In the late Jurassic, the Southern Indus Basin begins to develop because of the deviation of the Indian Plate from the Gondwana Plate and is deduced as an extensional area (Wandrey et al., 2004). Sembar Formation, age; Lower Cretaceous is the foremost hydrocarbon source rock for petroleum generation in the Southern Indus Basin, which is predominantly shale as well as sandstone, minor limestone, and siltstone as well (Aadil et al., 2014; Zaigham and Mallick, 2000). Sembar Formation age has been described by belemnite biostratigraphy as primarily Neocomian, which is Lower Cretaceous. It can also be ancient as the late Jurassic (Fatmi and AN, 1977).

There are lots of changes that occurred in the structural and stratigraphic characteristics of the Southern Indus Basin during the movement of Indian plate (Zaigham and Mallick, 2000; Kemal, 1991). In the early Cretaceous, the Indian Plate goes into warmer latitudes when it was detached from the Antarctic and Australian Plate, moves northward, whereas, at the same time towards the western ledge, the erosive surface has been overlain by Sembar and Goru Formation because of the occurrence of regional erosion in the Southern Indus Basin. In the west, Pab sandstone has been deposited due to the continuation of the shelf environment in the whole late Cretaceous time zone (Wandrey et al., 2004). In Late Cretaceous due to the continuous movement of the Indian Plate towards the north, a transform fault turns into active during flysch storage near the southern edge of the Indian Plate, and this phenomenon occurred in recent Cretaceous. The west part of the Indian Plate is sheared Southside due to which extensional faulting, reactivated (Kemal, 1991). When the Tethyan Sea winded up, an oblique collision occurred, and Sulaiman- Kirthar fold belt began to develop (Jadoon et al., 1994).

Figure. 1 Study area and well locations: (a) Sedimentary Basins of Pakistan; (b) Studied well located in the Southern Indus Basin.

Samples and Methodology

Seventy-eight samples of four different wells have been delivered by Oil and Gas Development Corporation Limited, Pakistan (OGDCL) whereas, well-logs are provided by the Directorate General of Petroleum Concession, Pakistan (DGPC) for this study.

Rock samples screening through the Rock-Eval method has been described by (Peters et al., 1986), in the absence of inert atmosphere (oxygen) warming organic matter to yield hydrocarbon mixtures. The heating extracts the free hydrocarbons, after which pyrolytic products from insoluble organic matter is cracked (kerogen). The primary top "S₁" characterizes thermally extracted (free) hydrocarbons from the rock at a temperature beneath 300°C. The place beneath the peak resembles significant free hydrocarbons bounded in the rock. S₁ (free hydrocarbons) may be produced in its natural position, or else they can exemplify migrated impurities and oil. Uncertainly the hydrocarbons are in situ produced. The values of S₁ underneath (0.2) are considered as deprived; those standards greater than 1.6 describe exquisite source rocks. The second top, "S₂," characterizes hydrocarbon mixtures as a consequence of kerogen cracking at a

temperature of nearly 300°C-550°C. The location of this height suits the remaining capability of the source rock. The organic matter producing prospective (S_2), is descriptive of the number of hydrocarbons manufactured through the transformation of kerogen within the rock. According to (Peters et al., 1986)(Bordenave and Leplat, 1993), the value of S_2 offers a concept of the extent of hydrocarbons, which may be produced by whole thermal transformation of kerogen under normal situations and is valuable to assess the propagative perspective of the source rocks.

Values of S_2 under 1.0 are considered as poor; values greater than ten are notable. The quantity of CO_2 launched from the cracking of kerogen is the peak of S_3 , which is noticed at the time of pyrolysis oven cooling. The values of S_1 and S_2 are calculated in mg HC/g rock. The values of S_3 are in mg CO_2 /g rock. T_{max} is the temperature at which the maximum magnitude of S_2 are produced (Espitalié and Burrus, 1986)(Peters et al., 2005). According to (Lafargue et al., 1998), throughout the previous two decades, numerous researchers have been using pyrolysis techniques to deliver statistics on maturity, type of organic matter, and potential in the source rocks. Clarification of Rock-Eval data is usually endorsed only in the situation of TOC of the sediments exceeds 0.5wt. % as inadequate organic matter guides to incorrect results owing to low signal to noise ratios and variable mineral matrix effects. The elementary parameters produced via the Rock-Eval technique are applied to deduce maturity, organic matter type, and genetic potential (Peters et al., 1986)(Peters and Cassa, 1994).

Results and discussions

Total Organic Carbon

TOC is used to measure the quantity of organic carbon in a rock (Jarvie, 1991). Its unit is wt.%. It is useful as a qualitative measure of hydrocarbon potential. It's essential to keep in mind that TOC falls with growing thermal maturity. According to (Hunt, 1995), for explaining a potential source rock, the TOC with 0.5wt. % is extensively considered as the minimal value. However, maximum geochemists reveal that rocks are having TOC <1wt. % as organically lean & not likely source for viable hydrocarbon accumulations. The average TOC of the shale source rock is 2.2 wt. %, and the all global shale average TOC is approximately 0.9wt. %, whereas the average mudstone (carbonate) rocks and shally calcareous rocks having 0.7wt. % & 1.9wt. % correspondingly. All global source rock average TOC is nearly 1.8wt. %. We are using here a TOC of 1.0wt. % as a

minimum standard for defining a petroleum source rock. The outcomes of TOC analysis of subsurface samples from the Well TE-1, Well TE-2, Well TE-3, and Well TE-4 (Table 1) are presented. Sembar formation with a value of 9.48wt. % from the sample of the subsurface at a depth of 3520m advocate it an excellent source rock (Bacon et al., 2000). As presented in the (Figure 2), the cross plot of Depth versus TOC, the fluctuations in the values of TOC against depth occurs in Sembar Formation samples in the Southern Indus Basin from Well TE-1, Well TE-2, Well TE-3, and Well TE-4, as the depth increases the TOC is also increases. The trend of the values in the cross plot is showing fair to very good source confirms it as a whole organic rich source rock. Thus the Lower Cretaceous Sembar Formation have the ability to produce unconventional shale oil and gas in the Southern Indus Basin. (Figure 2) (Maky and Ramadan, 2008).

Table. 1 Rock-Eval Pyrolysis and TOC data of the Sembar Formation of all wells

Well Name	Depth (m)	TOC (wt. %)	S ₁ (mg HC/g rock)	S ₂ (mg HC/g rock)	S ₃ (mg CO ₂ /g rock)	T _{max} (°C)	HI(mg HC/g TOC)	GP(mg HC/g rock)	PI(mg HC/g rock)	OI(mg CO ₂ /g TOC)	BI
Well TE-1	3352-3382	0.82 – 1.28 1.11(3)	0.2 – 0.38 0.30(3)	0.35 – 1.45 0.72(3)	0.05 – 1.03 0.53(3)	446 – 450 448(3)	29.03 – 113.28 61.6(3)	0.55 – 1.83 1.02(3)	0.2 – 0.47 0.34(3)	3.9 – 83.06 50.1(3)	0.24 – 0.29 0.26(3)
Well TE-2	4020-4052	1.1 – 1.21 1.16(4)	0.13 – 0.30 0.17(4)	0.45 – 0.55 0.47(4)	1.2 – 3.68 2.1(4)	434 – 447 442(4)	37.19 – 45.83 40.9(4)	0.58 – 0.85 0.65(4)	0.22 – 0.35 0.25(4)	109 – 306 181(4)	0.11 – 0.25 0.14(4)
Well TE-3	3482-3658	0.81 – 9.48 3.19(11)	0.23 – 10.16 3.27(11)	1.77 – 33.91 10.4(11)	1.73 – 4.88 3.63(11)	422 – 431 425(11)	154 – 505 275(11)	2.37 – 40.48 13.74(11)	0.09 – 0.38 0.26(11)	20 – 300 173(11)	0.69 – 1.72 0.96(11)
Well TE-4	3342-3914	0.55 – 1 = 3.0 1.94(60)	0.17 – 0.92 0.51(60)	0.01 – 1.87 0.78(60)	0.08 – 0.92 0.22(60)	389 – 488 455(60)	6.07 – 85.0 42(60)	0.26 – 1.99 1.3(60)	0.29 – 0.98 0.41(60)	4.42 – 94.73 13.19(60)	0.09 – 0.57 0.28(60)

Figure. 2 The Depth vs TOC cross plot shows the variations in TOC content with changing the depth of the Sembar Formation in different wells (modified after Maky and Ramadan, 2008).

Thermal Maturity and Types of Kerogen

The OM quality is a vital benchmark to estimate the hydrocarbon generation potential of a source rock [33,43,51]. The type and source of OM have been reflected through the van krevelen diagram (Figure 3)(Espitalie et al., 1977). HI vs T_{max} cross plot is used to detect the type of kerogen in the studied samples. (Figure 4) represents the cross plot between T_{max} and HI, which is showing the residual kerogen types in the studied Sembar Formation samples. The data from Well TE-1, Well TE-2, Well TE-3, and Well TE-4 showing dominantly the mature nature of the Sembar Formation except a few samples showing the immature nature.

Figure 4 presenting the relation b/w the type of kerogen and T_{max} in terms of HI. We can thoroughly divide the studied samples into two groups, totally based on T_{max} values, the primary is T_{max} more than 435°C, that's of the mature to an over-mature degree, and the second one is through a T_{max} of under 435°C, which indicates the immature degree. Samples of <435°C maybe because of the occurrence of non-indigenous hydrocarbons in the studied samples. In general, Lower Cretaceous Sembar Formation is well matured and mostly showing type II, type II/III, and type III kerogen, which is oil as well as gas prone. The HI and OI are used to describe the kerogen type and approximate level of maturation (Ghori, 1998). The kerogen is susceptible to oil having lower OI

and greater HI values, whereas the kerogen susceptible to gas is characterized by greater OI and lower HI values (Tissot and Welte, 1984). The (Krevelen, 1961) diagram, the cross plot between OI versus HI, displays a mix of kerogen type II & III within the Well TE-1, Well TE-2, Well TE-3, and Well TE-4 (Figure 3). Hence, Sembar Formation is matured enough to produce hydrocarbons in the Southern Indus Basin.

Figure. 3 HI vs. OI cross plot showing the distribution of different types of kerogen in the Sembar formation from different wells (modified after (Espitalie et al., 1977)).

Figure. 4 T_{max} vs. HI cross plot showing the maturity and types of kerogen in Sembar Formation from different wells (modified after (Hunt et al., 1995)).

Genetic potential of the source rock

Genetic potential provides a qualitative estimation of hydrocarbon resource potential, but unable to use to predict the type of Petroleum (oil or gas) produced at the time of pyrolysis (Tissot and Welte, 1984). Based on the cross plot between GP & TOC, the quality source rock and potentiality to produce Petroleum within Sembar Formation has been discovered. Poor-very good source rock quality has been shown from Well TE-1, Well TE-2, Well TE-3, and Well TE-4 within the Lower Cretaceous Sembar Formation samples (Figure 5). Based on the results of GP, Sembar Formation in the Southern Indus Basin have the potential to produce oil and gas.

Figure. 5 The cross plot shows the source rock quality, and the variations in TOC content and generation potential (GP) of Sembar Formation in different wells (modified after Ghori, 2002).

Migration of Hydrocarbons and the Expulsion History

Based on the PI & S_1 cross plot, we can distinguish between indigenous and non-indigenous hydrocarbons. The existence of non-indigenous hydrocarbons and relative thermal maturity of OM is usually measured using PI. Type I and II kerogens have the PI values greater than 0.1, whereas kerogen of type III frequently has the values in the margin of (0.1-0.2). The existence of non-indigenous hydrocarbons is identified based on lower TOC and higher S_1 values (Hunt et al., 1995). (Figure 6) indicating the cross plot between TOC vs. S_1 acquired from this research shows that the examined samples containing indigenous hydrocarbons. The cross plot between PI & T_{max} (Figure

7) adapted from (Ghori, 2000) shows many of the samples from different wells are in the mature stage and lie within the window of oil. However, few samples from Well TE-4 are post-mature, and some lie in the inert carbon window, while some samples from Well TE-3 and Well TE-4 lie in Stained or contaminated or Non-indigenous hydrocarbon window, which shows these samples are migrated from another area, or they have less potential of hydrocarbon generation. Additionally, many samples from Well TE-3 and Well TE-4 have the T_{max} value $<430^{\circ}\text{C}$ that might be possible because of the occurrence of migrated hydrocarbons (Peters et al., 1986; Shalaby et al., 2012).

The BI (bitumen index), also termed as migration index (Hunt et al., 1995), is used to govern the source rock depth where it starts to eject oil. The cross plot between BI vs Depth (Figure 8), the samples of Lower Cretaceous Sembar formation fall within the expected range of 0.1 to >0.4 , showing an expulsion of hydrocarbons. The cross plot of TOC versus S_1 of all wells displays an indigenous hydrocarbon (Figure 6). Therefore, the Formation is well matured, the existence of indigenous hydrocarbons, and the expulsion behaviour bring it into the category of very good source rock.

Figure. 6 The S_1 vs TOC (wt. %) cross plot is showing the indigenous occurrence of all the samples from different wells of Sembar Formation (modified after Hunt et al., 1995).

Figure. 7 The cross plot shows variations in the T_{max} , Production Index (PI), thermal maturity, and migration history of the hydrocarbons within the samples of Sembar Formation from different wells (modified after Ghori, 2000).

Figure. 8 The BI (S_1/TOC (wt. %)) vs Depth of Sembar Formation, all the samples fall within the expected range of 0.1 to >0.4, suggesting an expulsion of the hydrocarbons

Vitrinite reflectance measurement

In this research, four assessment wells (Well TE-1, Well TE-2, Well TE-3, and Well TE-4) has been used as a descriptive spot to simulate the hydrocarbon production and expulsion history of the Sembar Formation. The vitrinite reflectance of Sembar Formation in each well, calculated by the help of the burial history curve using PetroMod has shown in Figure 9-12. For figuring out the maturity of rocks, the vitrinite reflectance extents have usually been executed. In Sembar Formation source rock maturity lie in petroleum production range to outrageous of oil and gas condensate range based on the maturity tiers grounded on T_{max} and vitrinite reflectance R_o (%), and the occurrence different Maceral types, for example; exinite and alginite, fluorescent amorphous OM.

The organic-rich and poor rock durations in the samples of subsurface has been regularly noted. Associated sea-level agitations might restrain it, and the tectonics indicated in the shape of shallow-deep phases. The early cretaceous sea-level upward thrust & indigenous expansion of the basin is associated with a renewed phase of marine clastic sedimentation to the local tectonics within the research area. It is caused in the shallowing-deepening cycle of deposition, maintaining organic-rich to poor intervals within the Sembar Formation. R_o values of studied wells show that the Sembar Formation of Well TE-4 lies in Oil Window while Well TE-1, Well TE-2, and Well TE-3 lies in Dry Gas Windows.

Figure. 9 Vitrinite reflectance in Well TE-1 based on burial history.

Figure. 10 Vitrinite reflectance in Well TE-2 based on burial history.

Figure. 11 Vitrinite reflectance in Well TE-3 based on burial history.

Figure. 12 Vitrinite Reflectance in Well TE-4 based on burial history.

Geochemical logs

For the analysis of the basin, geochemical logging is a very beneficial means, amongst others. Hence some instances are present within the previous works (Clementz et al., 1979; Espitalie et al., 1977; Espitalié and Burrus, 1986; Magoon et al., 1987; MAGooN et al., 1984; Peters et al., 1986). The Cretaceous sediments from four different wells (Well TE-1, Well TE-2, Well TE-3, and Well TE-4) have been examined to show their usefulness for detecting free hydrocarbons and identifying source rocks using geochemical logs.

Well TE-1

The high-quality geochemical logs for well TE-1 (Figure 13) is based on closely spaced Rock-Eval pyrolysis & TOC data. Closely spaced samples allow critical evaluation of source and reservoir rock intervals. We have calculated all parameters with respect to depth (3345m-3385m). TOC values range from (0.82%-1.28%) with an average of 1.11%, which shows that with increasing depth, the TOC is going higher, which indicates that the source rock potential of Sembar Formation

in Well TE-1 is very good. S₁ & S₂ show low standards from poor to fair, as well as the samples, display lower HI values, and high values of OI. It indicates the Formation is gas prone & also proposing type II and III kerogen as the principal constituent of organic matter. Samples show poor-fair values of genetic potential, which indicates the Formation has fair source potential. Samples reveal T_{max} (446°C-450°C) & PI (0.2-0.47), which recommended the OM is matured, and it is the indication of good hydrocarbon generation. Sember Formation in Well TE-1 is a good candidate for source rock based on TOC and Rock-Eval pyrolysis data.

Figure. 13 Geochemical logs based on TOC and Rock-Eval pyrolysis parameters for Sember Formation sediments from Well TE-1, Southern Indus Basin.

Well TE-2

The TOC values of Sember Formation in Well TE-2 (Figure 14) ranges from (1.1%-1.21%) with an average of 1.16%, which reveals that, samples are in the range of petroleum products. S₁ and S₂ show low values, whereas samples also reveal lower HI values and high values of OI, which indicates the Formation is gaseous & also showing type III kerogen as the chief constituent of OM. GP values lie in a poor zone. The samples reveal T_{max} (434°C-447°C) & PI (0.2-0.35), which recommend the OM is matured, and it is the indication of good hydrocarbon generation. Sember

Formation in Well TE-2 is a good candidate for source rock based on TOC and Rock-Eval pyrolysis data.

Figure. 14 Geochemical logs based on TOC and Rock-Eval pyrolysis parameters for Sembar Formation sediments from Well TE-2, Southern Indus Basin.

Well TE-3

The TOC values of Sembar Formation in Well TE-3 (Figure 15) contains an extremely good amount of (0.81%-9.48%), with an average of 3.19%, which reveals samples are in the region of petroleum production. S₁ and S₂ show high values from (0.23-10.16, 1.77-33.91), which reveals that the Sembar Formation in Well TE-3 is a very good source for the generation of Petroleum. Samples express high values for both HI and OI, which indicates that this Formation has kerogen type II, type II/III & type III suggesting it is oil as well as gas prone. GP values lie in a fair-very good zone, which is also an indication of very good source rock. The samples exhibit T_{max} 422°C-431°C & PI 0.09-0.33 values. The Formation is immature, while PI values show the mature nature of the Formation. Based on the already generated and remaining prospective indicates, this

Formation is organic-rich, and it is situated within the oil window. Therefore, Sembar Formation is a noteworthy source for petroleum production within the Southern Indus Basin.

Figure. 15 Geochemical logs based on TOC and Rock-Eval pyrolysis parameters for Sembar Formation sediments from Well TE-3, Southern Indus Basin.

Well TE-4

Sembar Formation in Well TE-4 (Figure 16) corresponds within the range of good-excellent TOC (0.9%-2.93%), with an average of 1.95%. S₁ and S₂ show low values from poor-fair, which reveals that the Sembar Formation in Well TE-4 has fair hydrocarbon generation potential. The samples display lower values for both HI and OI, which indicates that this Formation has kerogen type III and suggesting it is susceptible to gas. GP values lie in the poor-fair zone. The samples exhibit T_{max} (422°C-488°C) and PI (0.29-0.98), some samples of Sembar Formation lie in the immature zone, and most of the samples lie in a mature zone. In contrast, some lie in post-mature, which exhibits the Sembar shale is a worthy source for hydrocarbon production, while PI values show the mature and post-mature nature of the Formation. The samples comprise of a great extent of total organic carbon (TOC), reasonable thermal maturity & genetic potential (GP), adequately

great to produce oil and gas. Thus Sembar Formation is a noteworthy source for petroleum production within the Southern Indus Basin.

Figure. 16 Geochemical logs based on TOC and Rock-Eval pyrolysis parameters for Sembar Formation sediment from Well TE-4, Southern Indus Basin.

Comparison of Results with International Standards

Comparison of whole outcomes with international standards, Table 2 indicates the establishment of a shale gas reservoir.

Table 2. Results compared with international standards (modified after Haider et al., 2012).

S.No.	Parameter	Standards	Our Results	Remarks
1	TOC (wt. %)	1%-5%	0.8%-2.05%	Good
2	Thermal Maturity (R_o)	1.00-1.4	1.5	Good
3	Kerogen Type	II/III	II & III	Good
4	Depth(meters)	1000-5000	3300-4800	Good
5	T_{max}	>430°C	450°C -485°C	Good

Conclusion

1. The Lower Cretaceous Sembar Formation in the study area is mainly composed of shales and minor traces of siltstone and sandstone.
2. Sembar Formation in the Southern Indus Basin is organically rich with an average TOC of (2.05 wt. %).
3. The shales of Sembar Formation has adequate potential to generate hydrocarbons. The mean genetic potential is 4.69 mg HC/g rock.
4. The HI values range from 5.96-505 mg HC/g TOC with an average value of 144.45 mg HC/g TOC. Whereas, the OI values range from 3.90-306.66 mg CO₂/g TOC with an average value of 45.43 mg CO₂/g TOC.
5. The Hydrogen Index data, HI vs. Tmax cross plot, and Van krevelen Diagram (HI vs. OI) show the Sembar Formation has type II & type III kerogen, which are mainly oil and gas prone.
6. Organic-rich shales of the Lower Cretaceous Sembar Formation in the Southern Indus Basin are thermally mature in nature. The average Tmax values are (450 °C), the mean Production Index is 0.38, whereas the calculated Vitrinite Reflectance based on burial history is 1.5 (%).
7. On the basis of current investigations, it is concluded that sufficient vertical thickness of organic-rich facies, their lateral continuity, High TOC content, appropriate Kerogen type, thermal maturity reflecting oil– gas generation zone, an indigenous hydrocarbon exists within the Formation. Thus the Sembar Formation has the potential to produce unconventional hydrocarbons in the Southern Indus Basin.

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Dedication

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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